

WORDS THAT MODIFY IN FOOD NAMES

Davlyatova Elvira Muradovna

PhD ,Teacher of the Faculty of Foreign

Philology of Termiz State University

Fayzullayeva Manzura

Student of Termiz State University

Faculty of Foreign Philology 4 courses

Abstract: In the past, from very ancient times, peoples lived by establishing mutual neighborly relations. These relations have influenced various aspects of culture, and in turn, the enrichment of languages due to external factors. Among other things, the relationship between the Uzbek and Chinese peoples goes back to the distant past. There is information in the sources that some plants and trees were brought to China from Turkestan and cultivated. It is also known that some dishes of Chinese cuisine were adopted by the Uzbek people mainly through the Uyghurs. All these processes served to enrich our language with Chinese words. This article is devoted to changes in form and meaning of words that have been adopted from Chinese.

Key words: idioms, manti, ginseng, lagmon, tea

INTRODUCTION There is no language in the world whose vocabulary consists only of its own words. Words taken from other languages in that language either keep their form as it is, or adapt to its nature, grammatical structure, word formation, spelling and pronunciation rules [Aliyev, Sodikov, 1994: 18]. It is important that the acquisition of foreign words does not mean that the language is poor. Perhaps the meaning of the word that is being assimilated for the people speaking this language may mean that it was previously foreign.

The transfer of words from language to language occurs due to a certain social need of society. Adoptive words are realized as a linguistic possibility that fulfills this need. At each stage of the development of society, borrowing from outsiders has different forms and different character. Words in the language increase based on internal and external factors, and this increase, in a certain sense, determines the development of the language. Borrowing a foreign word is a foreign word of the nation, the nation "Understanding different cultures, nations, languages through comparative-typological research 2" 15th International Scientific Conference 3(20), March, 2023 with the language community, economic, cultural , is a real indication of his spiritual connection, friendly relationship with them [Berdialiyev, 2019: 57].

It is known that cultural relations between Central Asia and China go back to ancient times. The creation of the Great Silk Road started a new stage of not only economic and political, but also cultural development. This, in turn, is reflected in the history of the language. That is, it created interlanguage exchange of words. In Uzbek linguistics, the grammatical features of borrowed words are studied in different aspects. These studies are about the words that came into our language from Eastern and Western languages. Among them, there are very few studies aimed at revealing the linguistic processes of words adopted from Chinese into the Uzbek language [For details, see: Komilova, 2022: 372-376].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

A. Khodzhayev and other scientists' work "From the history of Uzbekistan-China relations" lists some of the plants and foods that were brought from Turkestan to China through the Great Silk Road. "For example, such plants as mosh khudou), sedana (ʌM xumo), turnip (ʌh khuluobu), pumpkin huguo), coriander (ʌʌMʌ khusuy), almond khutou) are among these. Usually the people of Turkestan are called Chinese They added this word to the name of the plants brought from this region due to the general name "xu" [Khodjajev, Karimova et al., 2022: 26]

In the explanatory dictionary edited by A. Madvaliyev, 17 words are given as belonging to the Chinese language. 5 of them are food names [Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language, volumes II, IV, 2008: 80, 493, 503, 539, 581]. 1. Ginseng (Hit. "man-root") is a medicinal plant that grows in the Far East and China. Ginseng is a root-like plant that grows wild in the forested areas of the Far East.

2. Lag'mon (Hit. ÎÈM lamian "long dough"). Food made by stretching or cutting the dough long and thin, and eating it with cabbage on the face. My silver sister was also here. As they did not like Lag'mon very much, it seems that they did not get better. A. Qadiri. Days gone by.

3. Manti (Hit. jj^c mantou Myan-khamir+ti-meat) is a dish made by mixing minced meat and onion in dough and cooking it in a pan. What is chuchvara, Brother Sidiqjon, I will make it into oily manti. Make the dough thinner or thicker? A. Cairo. Twin lights.

4. Tea (t.f. < hit. cha) 1. An evergreen bush tree, a bush, whose leaves are drunk, growing in southern countries. Tea plantations. 2. The leaves of this plant are specially processed, ground, and drunk as a tincture. Blue tea. Indian tea. Ceylon tea. Georgian tea. A drop of tea. Tea box. 3. Aromatic drink brewed from specially processed, crushed leaves of this plant. Indian drink will be real tea. "Gulnorpari" 4. Eating with this drink. At the tea place, sometimes laughing, sometimes crying, he talked about himself and his children. A. Cairo. Koshchinor lanterns [For more on the word tea, see: Komilova, 2023: 249-253].

5. Shircoy (Persian+Chinese - milk tea) Milk boiled with tea, salt, butter and pepper. To drink Shircoy.

Our language also has some words borrowed from Chinese, but not listed in this dictionary. We will list some of them below.

Sai is a salad made from radish ^ (cai). In Uyghur language: 1) salad prepared by mixing cabbage and partially meat; 2) a snack made from greens in general. Compare again, in Uighur: sey samsa-kok somsa; Seykhana - a warehouse where vegetables are stored (Hit. tsai-taj.house).

Jusai - ^^ (jusai) is a green that is fragrant and eaten as a side dish. In Uighur, jusey means fragrant onion.

Shiman is thinly sliced lagmon. Shimen in Uighur. Chinese Simian (si-thin, mian-cut dough, ugra); Manti is a dish made with meat or pumpkin in the middle of the dough and baked in the oven [Aliyev, Sodikov, 1994: 31].

"Understanding different cultures, nations, languages through comparative-typological studies 2" 15th international scientific conference

3(20), March, 2023

Manpar - M^ (mianpian) is a type of dough prepared by cutting the dough into strips, then cutting it off and adding it to the soup [Aliyev, Sodikov, 1994: 31].

Hoshan is a type of food, which is made with minced meat, pumpkin, potatoes, wrapped in oil and sometimes cooked in foil [Aliyev, Sadikov, 1994: 31-32].

Yuto - M^í (yóu tazi(yu) yutoza is a food that is made by rolling out the dough, applying oil and making it into a funnel shape, and cooking it as a veil. In Uyghur, jutoza, in Chinese, yutaszi (yu - oil, tower, tower) [Aliyev, Sadiqov , 1994: 32].

Laza - Mí (lazi) is a paste prepared by frying chopped garmdori in oil. In Uighur, laza means red garmdori. Laszi in Chinese [Aliyev, Sodikov, 1994: 32]. When comparing the above words with their original Chinese, it can be observed that they have both sound and meaning changes.

CONCLUSION.

Interestingly, some of these words are increasingly "Uzbekized". Especially words that mean food names. For example, manti, lagman, manpar, etc. are on the list of Uzbek national dishes in the restaurants operating under the "National dishes" brand today. If one of these dishes is prepared in our homes, none of us will feel like we are eating Chinese food. Of course, this phenomenon may be related to the fact that the preparation technology of the named foods has also changed. But the important

part of the matter for us is that today we do not even think that the names of these dishes are originally from Chinese. Also, the processes related to the smooth addition of form-forming (sometimes word-forming, for example, mantichi, mantipaz) additions to these words, like originally Turkic words, attract one's attention.

The bottom line is that words borrowed from other languages into any language "start to look" like words of their own layer as a result of a certain period of time. In our opinion, it is important that the form and meaning aspect of the word is preserved or changed in this language process. Therefore, one should be extremely careful when talking about their etymology.

Names of food that have been adopted into our language from the Chinese language are also important as a product of the linguistic and cultural process. They indicate that the cultural ties between the Uzbek and Chinese peoples go back to the distant past.

REFERENCES:

1. Aliyev A., Sodiqov Q. O'zbek adabiy tili tarixidan. Toshkent: "O'zbekiston", 1994. 120 b.
2. Berdialiyev A. O'zbek sinxron sotsiolingvistikasi. - Toshkent, 2019. - 129 b.
3. Komilova M. O'zbek tilshunosligida o'zlashma leksemalarning o'rganilishi tarixi // FarDU. Ilmiy xabarlar, 2022 №6ro - B. 372-376.
4. Komilova M. Choy so'zining tarixi xususida // Namangan davlat universiteti ilmiy axborotnomasi. NamDU, 2023. - B. 249-253.
5. O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. II, IV tomlar. A.Madvaliyev tahriri ostida. - Toshkent: "O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi" Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2008. 493-b.
6. Xodjayev A., Karimova N. va boshq. O'zbekiston - Xitoy munosabatlari tarixidan. - Toshkent: "Fan ziyosi", 2022. - 216 b.
- 7.

https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=2s19h9gAAAAJ&citation_for_view=2s19h9gAAAAJ:_FxGoFyzp5QC